

ACCOUNTABILITY AND FINANCIAL REGULATIONS IN NIGERIA'S PUBLIC SECTOR

UMANAHA, NSIKAN JOHN

**Department of Accountancy, School of Business and Management
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpenne**
nsikanumanah2013@gmail.com

EKPOESE, JOHN DOMINIC

**Department of Accountancy, School of Business and Management
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpenne**
ekpoese09@yahoo.com

&

UMOH, NSIKAK HENRY

**Department of Accountancy, School of Business and Management
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, Ikot Ekpenne**
henryn2014@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper is aimed at finding out the relationship between accountability and financial regulations in the Nigerian public sector; with the objective of examining the effect of accountability on the financial regulations. The population of the study consists of 120 staff of the ministry of Finance and Internal Revenue Service in Uyo, Akwa Ibom. Census sampling technique was adopted and a sample of 120 staff was used for the study. Data for the study was obtained using primary and secondary sources. Linear regression analysis was used to analyze the data collected with the aid of SPSS to examine the relationship between accountability and financial regulations. The study revealed that there is a positive relationship between reporting compliance, legislative control, and Treasury Single Account. The study, therefore, recommends that more attention should be paid to strengthening the regulatory institutions and robust framework to ensure public accountability.

Keywords: Accountability, Financial Regulations, Legislative Control and Treasury Single Account (TSA).

Introduction

The ability for any government to function effectively and efficiently is heavily reliant on the methodology established by that government to handle economic materials and reduce spending in order to prevent needless and inefficient expenditure. Because the principal role of government is to offer social infrastructure

and establish an environment that makes it possible for citizens to achieve maximum possibilities, resources available must all be conservatively controlled, utilized, and controlled for the benefit of every citizen (Suleiman, 2009). A government aiming at achieving her Millennium Development Goal (MDG) must embrace accountability in her public sector as a means of fine-tuning her institutions and the officials to work towards meeting the expectations and aspirations of the citizen who own the resources which government holds on trust.

Accountability is a dedication to demonstrate that the job was performed in conformity with established guidelines and requirements, and that the officer reports performance results with integrity and precision in reference to mandated roles and planning processes. It entails acting in a straightforward and legal manner, and it also involves providing advice. Government oversight is essential for the operation of our political structure because accountability necessitates those charged with creating or enacting policies to provide an explanation to the public (Onochie, 2006).

Nigeria is a federation of states and local government councils with a multi-ethnic population and abundant natural and mineral resources, with the mandate of equally developing all segments of the country. This requires strong institutions that are effectively and efficiently manned by men and women of impeccable character and inclination toward national goals (Akinbuli, 2013). This is referred to as the public sector or public service. The enabling rules and relevant legislation charge it with collective action public resources, collecting and allocating all funds for the common good. The responsibility principle is based on trust, faith, fairness, integrity, and precautionary handling of government funds.

As a result, there is a strong need for officers entrusted with public wealth management to provide complete, relevant, and accurate information about their stewardship of public funds. To accomplish this effectively, laws and regulatory frameworks have been put in place to regulate the general conduct of officers and institutions, as well as to set parameters for communicating their stewardship to all who demand accountability (Okwoli, 2004).

However, because of an absence of honesty and openness, public institutions that would be recognized as that of the supervisor of taxpayer funds by trust, avenue, and mechanism for national development have lost public trust. Fraudulent transactions have become so common in the Nigerian public sector, according to Appah and Appiah (2010) that it appears that every component of the public sector is involved in some form of these heinous crimes. According to Kenneth, despite the country's

numerous regulatory requirements, federal agencies, agencies, boards, and departments do not ensure adherence to responsibility concepts (2012). This assertion is consistent with that of Akinbuli (2013), who stated that public officers' duties and trust are not carried out effectively and efficiently. There has been a disregard for regulatory laws and the principle of accountability.

The vast majority of government institutions do not maintain adequate financial documents as mandated by the law, and they merely release accounting reports and reviewing financial statements to the general public on rare occasions when they are due primarily to increased scrutiny. Financial mismanagement, ineffectiveness, inefficiency, maladministration, and a lack of accountability have plagued Nigeria's public sector. Openness in administration of the national money gives rise to conspiracy to commit contract mismanagement, malfeasance such as the siphoning of significant effect for infrastructural development into personal bank accounts overseas, the theft of national assets, unapproved internal revenue for the government, awarding of contractual agreements to family and friends without the ability to fulfill them, resulting in numerous failed projects; salary payouts to ghost workers, accessible embezzlement of retirement funds, a complete absence of precise documentation of operational costs expenses, financial mismanagement, as well as a lack of budget implementation, among other things.

1.2 The Study's Objectives

The study's main goal was to look into the effect of financial regulatory laws on accountability in the Nigerian public sector. The specific objectives were to:

- i. investigate the impact of reporting compliance on fiscal prudence in the Nigerian public sector;
- ii. assess the impact of legislative control on fiscal prudence in the Nigerian public sector;
- iii. examine the effect of the Treasury Single Account (TSA) on fiscal prudence in the Nigerian public sector; and
- iv. assess the effect of financial regulation on fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector.

1.3 Research Questions

- i. How does reporting conformity affects fiscal prudence in the Nigerian public sector?
- ii. What effect does legislative oversight have on fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector?
- iii. How does the Financial Institution Account (TSA) affect fiscal prudence in the

- Nigerian government?
- iv. How does financial regulation affect fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector?

1.4 The Study's Hypotheses

The following hypotheses, stated in null forms, were derived from the study objectives:

- Ho1:** Reporting requirements compliance has little impact on fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector.
- Ho2:** Legislative oversight of the Nigerian public sector has little impact on fiscal conservatism.
- Ho3:** The Treasury Single Account (TSA) has had no significant impact on fiscal prudence in the Nigerian public sector.
- Ho4:** Financial regulation has little impact on the Nigerian government's fiscal prudence.

Related Literature Review

The researchers examined the relevant works in three broad categories: conceptual review, conceptual literature review, and empirical review.

2.1 Conceptual Review

The researchers examined the concept of responsibility, accountability principles, transparency, and nepotism in the public sector, as well as various financial regulatory laws and structures, in the conceptual review.

2.1.1 Accountability is a Concept.

According to Adegbite (2010), accountability is the goal of demonstrating that work was completed in accordance with established procedures and preconditions. According to Johnson (2004), government oversight is a necessary component for our political system to function because accountability requires those in charge of policy formulation and/or implementation to explain actions to constituents. He also claimed that the capacity to accomplish complete visibility was and still is woefully insufficient, owing to the framework of accountability itself, as well as the additional accessibility of goals and associated individual responsibility expectations. As a result, he proposed that in order to fully reveal responsibility, it must be deliberately engineered, along with its positive and productive aspects. Beyond the naming and arresting of officials or the pursuit of shady details, the goal of accountability should be to pursue quality objectives financial planning improvements in a bid to lower the rate of organizational recidivism.

According to Onochie (2001), accountability includes the obligation to do one's duty honestly and forthrightly, as well as the responsibility to provide data that can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of such services, as well as being willing to take responsibility and directly be accountable to someone for some actions. Responsibility is divided into two stages:

(a) Answer-ability: This requires the government, its law enforcement agencies, and government officials to not only offer relevant information about their choices and behaviours, but should well as justify them to the general public and those willing to assume responsibility for institutions alleged of supervision, control and governance.

(b) Enforcement: This suggests that the general public or even the management system in charge of accountability can reprimand the alleged infringer and correct the infringing behavior. As a result, one or both of these stages may be overseen by primarily referred institutions.

According to Bovens (2007), disclosure is a critical component of effective governance. It concerns the relationship between the state and its citizens, as well as the state's accountability for its actions. Thus, in the public sector, accountability refers to the legal and reporting framework, organizational structure, strategies, procedures, and actions that help ensure that any individual or institution that uses public funds and makes decisions that affect people's lives can be held accountable for their actions. He also believes that government accountability is led by a number of entities, agencies, and institutions rather than a single entity. Accountability is demonstrated by Members of Parliament, public entities, courts and tribunals, inquiry agencies, and, in many cases, oversight by civil society and the media.

2.1.2. The Principles of Public Accountability

Disclosure, benevolence, truthfulness, trust, and fiscal discipline are critical elements for public sector accountability.

Transparency: This makes reference to how open a government entity is about its actions, or the amount of information it does provide regarding what it is doing, where and how it is happening, and how well it is performing. Democratic government will encourage public debate, which will increase transparency throughout the public sector and focus on promoting more equitable, effective, and efficient governance. Responding to information requests is part of being transparent. It is about providing people with the knowledge they require to take part in choices that impact people.

- **Fairness:** It is about solving a problem in a reasonable and objective manner. In practice, this means that investigators must act objectively and independently, and that all relevant information must be thoroughly reviewed without undue delay. Most of the time, acting fairly entails giving the group subject to the perceived injustice the opportunity to comment on any adverse findings made against them before reaching a final action.
- **Integrity:** Integrity in the context of public sector accountability means exercising power in accordance with the values, goals, and responsibilities entrusted to or held by public entities and individual office holders. Integrity ensures that private attachments and interests do not taint the government's estimates and budget.

Fiscal Prudence: Authorization of projects and behavior patterns with economic consequences by a legitimate representative, conveyed in an annual or medium-term budget and structure to ensure that no actions are taken during the economic management process to affect the country's fiscal ability. Every policy and action is designed to ensure that the government's spending is efficient and does not waste money.

Adegbite (2010) summarizes the public accountability principles as follows:

- Transparency entails gathering information and making it available and accessible to the public for review.
- Availability of evidence or justification, which entails having a clear rationale for decisions and actions, including those that are not implemented, in order for them to be properly interrogated.
- Compliance, as measured by monitoring and evaluating procedures and outcomes, as well as transparency in reporting those findings; and
- Sanctions or enforcement for failures to comply, justify, or be transparent. As a result, accountability is inextricably linked to organizational purpose and public trust rather than adhering to regulations or regulatory requirements.

2.1.3. Financial Regulatory Laws/ Framework

The 1999 Constitution: The Federal Republic of Nigeria's constitution is the primary and supreme legal document governing government financial management, accounting, and reporting. The following key areas of government accounting are addressed in the constitution. Controls for audit and investigation are built into the accounting system as is the appropriation procedure. It establishes, among other things, the consolidated revenue fund and the Federation Account. It describes how to move funds from the consolidated revenue fund.

1958 Finance (Control and Management) Act: In accordance with constitutional principles, this Act governs the administration and use of administration funds. It defines the accounting system that must be maintained, as well as the rules that must be followed when attempting to prepare accounts and financial statements. The most significant aspect of the Act is that it controls the format and presentation of government financial reports. It also specifies which securities should be included in the government's portfolio and the principles to be used in valuing government investments.

Appropriation Acts: Appropriation Acts are created when Money Bills become laws. They govern financial matters such as Consolidated Revenue Fund payments and withdrawals. Every year, Appropriation Acts are passed to authorize the release of public funds for the purpose of providing services during the fiscal year to which they apply. With the exception of the Contingencies Fund and the Consolidated Revenue Fund, Appropriation Acts may direct adjustments in the operating condition of any fund.

The Financial Regulations (FR): This is a versatile accounting and control document. Its primary function is to serve as a regulatory code. It also serves as a framework for action, encompassing a variety of techniques or standardization documentation of specific financial transactions, events, and positions, but equally important functions. According to Oshisami (1997), financial regulations define the requirements for standardization in accounting system design, as well as the framework within which deviation is or will be permitted.

The Audit Act 1956: This Act governs audit and accountability in the federal government, along with some sections of the Nigerian constitution.

Legislative control: The Nigerian legislature controls and regulates revenue and expenditure estimates for any fiscal year. Members of the National Assembly must thoroughly scrutinize budget estimates to ensure that government revenue and expenditures are accurate, effective, and efficient.

A Treasury Single Account (TSA) is a system of government bank accounts that functions as a functional and design of the government's available funds. A Treasury Single Account (TSA) is a bank account or group of linked accounts that the government uses to conduct all receipts and payments in accordance with the treasury unity concept. The TSA has full control of the federal government's cash

reserves; and because it consolidates cash resources, TSA aggregate cash control is an important component of financial and budget management.

Theory Review

Several theories can be used to explain the issue of accountability in the public sector. Some of these theories are discussed further below.

The Stakeholder Model: The stakeholder model, according to Freeman (1994), holds that certain people or organizations are critical to the institution's long-term survival. This is known as organizational interpretation. Stakeholder theory seeks to clarify, support, and acquire leadership options that include and compromise a wide range of objectives. Since its inception, this school of thought has received a great deal of attention and support.

Stewardship Theory: As a result of a seminar work, stewardship theory was also developed (Donaldson & Davis, 1989). The importance of senior managers acting as organizational stewards and ensuring that everything is done in the best interests of the principal was emphasized in this study. In their interpretation of stewardship theory, they established that most managers tend to act in the best interests of their company by emphasizing the company's collaborative goal rather than their self-serving option. They also discovered that the majority of stewards are motivated solely by the desire to make the best decision, which is usually in the best interests of the organization, because stewards believe that the best action will benefit them in the long run. Davis, Schoorman, and Donaldson (1997) define the theory as the process by which public administrators protect and ensure maximum wealth of shareholders.

Empirical Review

Akinbuli (2013) investigates the Nigerian public sector's accountability. A total of 130 people took part in the study, including staff and practitioners from the Ministries of Finance and Justice, as well as Chartered Accountants in Public Practice. The sample was chosen using simple random and purposive sampling techniques. Percentages and the chi-square statistical method were used to analyze the data set. According to the findings of the study, 83% of respondents agreed that public officials must account to the public for their stewardship while in office, and 63% believed the budget was incomplete at the end of the fiscal year. Simply put, a lack of accountability impedes Nigeria's growth and resource allocation. The findings also revealed that abuses of power committed by law enforcement officers are either delayed, incomplete, or swept under the rug, never to be seen again. According to the researcher, adherence to legal instruments requiring public officials to account to the public is extremely low, contributing to Nigeria's democratic oversight failure.

Avery and Obeh (2018) used an organized questionnaire survey to assess the impact of budgetary management and accountability in the public sector. The population of the study included 115 Bayelsa State Board of Internal Revenue employees (SBIR). 89 samples were determined using the Taro Yamani method. Percentages were used to analyze the collected data. To explain the relationship between variables, a simple regression model was used. According to the findings, 79.7% of respondents agreed that having an internal auditing system in place helps to raise the level of obligation within the organization. Internal control (as measured by risk assessment, control procedures, and an effective communication and dissemination system) was found to have a significant positive relationship with accountability in the public sector, as demonstrated by a coefficient correlation (R) of 86.3% and a coefficient of determination (R²) of 74.4%, implying that effective internal controlled institutions can explain only 25.6% of variation in accountability.

Methodology

This section discusses the research design, population, sample size, sampling technique, data sources and nature, theoretical and empirical model specifications, variable measurement, and data analysis method.

3.1 Research Design

The researcher used a survey research design in this study. This enabled the researcher to use questionnaires to elicit respondents' opinions on financial regulatory laws and accountability issues in the Nigerian public sector.

3.2 Sample Size

The researcher determined the size of the survey for the study in accordance with population diameter of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents.

3.4 Sampling Technique

The census sampling technique was used, and the entire study population was examined.

3.5 Sources and Nature of Data

The relevant data for this study came from primary sources. The primary data was gathered using questionnaires distributed to the recipient's chosen participants. The data came from Akwa Ibom State's Uyo Local Government Area finance department.

3.6 Reliability of Data

Cronbach's Alpha Statistics was used to evaluate study's data dependence. The researcher considers Cronbach's Alpha statistics of 50% or higher to be significant, indicating that the data is reliable.

3.7 Theoretical Specification of Models

The data in this study was analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression models. Table 3.1 depicts the measurement and a priori expectation for each of the independent variables on the dependent.

Table 3.1: Variable Description

S/N	Variable	Abbr.	Measurement	Apriori Expectation
1.	Fiscal Prudence	FP	Five-Point Likert Scale	-
2.	Reporting Compliance	RC	Five-Point Likert Scale	Positive
3.	Legislative Control	LC	Five-Point Likert Scale	Positive
4.	Treasury Single Account	TSA	Five-Point Likert Scale	Positive
5.	Financial Regulation	FR	Five-Point Likert Scale	Positive

Source: *Researcher's Compilation, 2021*

3.8 Empirical Specification of Model

The study's model and all variables are listed below:

Fiscal Prudence (FP) was the dependent variable, while the independent variables were Reporting Compliance (RC), Legislative Control (LC), Treasury Single Account (TSA), and Financial Regulation (FR).

The model was as follows:

$$FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RC + \beta_2 LC + \beta_3 TSA + \beta_4 FR + et \dots$$

Equation (3.1), where β_0 is the FP intercept and 1, 2, 3, and 4 are the coefficients of the independent variables; et is the random error term.

3.9 Methods of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, simple percentages, multiple linear regression models, correlation coefficients R , R-Square, Adjusted R-Square, variance inflation factor (VIF), Tolerance, t-statistic (t-stat), F-ratio, and P-value. These data analysis methods are appropriate for this study because they will allow for the quantification of dependent and independent variables in the investigation of Nigerian financial regulatory laws and accountability issues. VIF and Acceptance were used to test the independent variables for multicollinearity. As a result, the analysis was conducted at the 5% level of significance, with the following decision

rules: accept H_0 and reject H_1 when P-value is greater than 0.05; accept H_1 and reject H_0 when P-value is less than 0.05.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Findings

In this section of the study, the details of analysis, interpretation and discussion of the findings were presented in order to provide empirical results for the study.

4.1 Data Presentation

The data for the study were collected and presented on the table shown below:

Table 4.1: Data Presentation

S/N	QUESTIONS	SA	A	U	D	SD
1.	The ministry is in compliance with various reporting regulations	100	20	0	0	0
2.	The ministry is operating under legislative control	98	22	0	0	0
3.	TSA has been fully adopted and implemented in the ministry	102	18	0	0	0
4.	Financial regulatory laws ensure commensurable sanctions or remedy for contravening behavior in public sector	104	16	0	0	0
5.	Fiscal prudence is expected to be maintained in Nigeria public sector	110	10	0	0	0

Source: *Field Survey, 2021*

From Table 4.1 above, it could be asserted that the ministry is in compliance with various reporting regulations; the ministry is operating under legislative control; TSA has been fully adopted and implemented in the ministry; financial regulatory laws ensure commensurable sanctions or remedy for contravening behaviors in public sector, and fiscal prudence is expected to be maintained in Nigeria's public sector.

4.2 Data Analysis

Under the data analysis, the various data collected by the researcher of this study were analyzed in order to arrive at empirical results. These were shown accordingly below:

4.2.1 Reliability Tests

The Cronbach's Alpha Statistics was computed to test the reliability of the relevant data collected for the study. The computations are presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Reliability Statistics

Variable	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
FP	18.2253	5.961	0.765	0.685	0.959
RC	18.3191	5.447	0.914	0.896	0.936
LC	18.3695	4.945	0.948	0.926	0.926
TSA	18.4710	4.357	0.871	0.818	0.950
FR	18.3660	4.738	0.945	0.920	0.925
Aggregate					0.951

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2021

From Table 4.2 above, the Cronbach's Alpha Statistics of 95.1% in aggregate showed that the relevant data collected for the study were reliable because of the fact that coefficient computed was significant. The individual statistics for the reliability tests were also significant as presented above.

4.2.2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for each of the variables such as FP, RC, LC, TSA and FR were computed and presented on the Table 4.3 below:

Table 4.3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation (N)	Minimum (MIN)	Maximum (MAX)	Mean	STD
FP	120	4.00	5.00	4.7125	0.45281
RC	120	3.00	5.00	4.6186	0.50490
LC	120	1.00	5.00	4.5683	0.60424
TSA	120	1.00	5.00	4.4667	0.79048
FR	120	1.00	5.00	4.5717	0.65408

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2021

From Table 4.3 above, for Financial Prudence (FP), mean value (average) stood at 4.713, maximum value of 5, minimum value was 4 and standard deviation was 0.4528. This indicated that the variation from the mean value was not high for the collected data. The observation of 120 was obtained by multiplying the sample size of 120 respondents to the number of questions in relation to FP.

For Reporting Compliance (RC), mean value (average) stood at 4.619, maximum value of 5, minimum value was 3 and standard deviation was 0.505. This indicated that the variation from the mean value was not high for the obtained data. The observation of 120 was obtained by multiplying the sample size of 120 respondents to the number of questions in relation to RC.

For Legislative Control (LC), mean value (average) stood at 4.568, maximum value of 5, minimum value was 1 and standard deviation was 0.6042. This showed that the variation from the mean value was not high for the obtained data. The observation of 120 was obtained by multiplying the sample size of 120 respondents to the number of questions in relation to LC.

For Treasury Single Account (TSA), mean value (average) stood at 4.467, maximum value of 5, minimum value was 1 and standard deviation was 0.790. This showed that the variation from the mean value was not high for the obtained data.

120 observations were obtained by multiplying the sample size of 120 respondents to the number of questions in relation to TSA.

For Financial Regulation (FR), mean value (average) stood at 4.572, maximum value of 5, minimum value was 1 and standard deviation was 0.6541. This indicated that the variation from the mean value was not high for the obtained data. The observation of 120 was obtained by multiplying the sample size of 120 respondents to the number of questions in relation to FR.

4.2.3 Test of Multi-Collinearity

The correlation of each of the variables were computed and presented as shown on Table 4.4 below:

Table 4.4: Correlation Matrix

Variable	FP	RC	LC	TSA	FR
FP	1.000	0.820	0.732	0.678	0.726
RC		1.000	0.213	0.189	0.299
LC			1.000	0.280	0.347
TSA				1.000	0.289
FR					1.000

Source: *Researcher's Computation, 2021*

From the correlation matrix Table 4.4 above, there was no multi-collinearity in all the independent variables because they all had correlation coefficient with each independent variable of less than 0.8 (80%). The relationship between RC and FP was 0.820 (82.0%); the relationship between LC and FP was 0.732 (73.2%); the relationship between TSA and FP was 0.678 (67.8%) and the relationship between FR and FP was 0.726 (72.6%).

4.2.4 Test of Autocorrelation

The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 2.038 shown on the Table 4.5 below indicated that there was no first order autocorrelation in the model.

4.2.5 Coefficient of Determination

The R^2 for all the independent variables were computed and presented the Table 4.5 as shown below:

Table 4.5: Coefficient of Determination

R^2	Adjusted R^2	F-ratio	Durbin-Watson (DW) Statistic
0.685	0.684	634.589 (P<0.05)	2.038

Source: *Researcher's Computation, 2021*

*Dependent Variable=FP

From Table 4.5 above, R^2 (Adjusted) showed that exactly 68.4% changes in FP can be explained by the influence of RC, LC, TSA and FR while 31.6% are attributable to other variables not included in the model of the present study. The F-ratio computed indicated that both R^2 and Adjusted R^2 were significant (634.589, P-value<0.05). This implied that variables of financial regulatory laws (RC, LC, TSA and FR) exerted joint and significant influence on FP in Nigeria's public sector.

4.2.6 Test of Hypotheses

The coefficients of each of the independent variables and other statistics were computed and presented on Table 4.6 as shown below:

Table 4.6: Multiple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Statistic	P-Value	Remark	Tolerance	VIF
Constant	1.333	18.530	0.000	Significant		
RSP	0.859	22.588	0.000	Significant	0.602	1.660
TDP	0.170	3.802	0.000	Significant	0.792	1.263
EM	0.141	6.511	0.000	Significant	0.767	1.303
RS	0.096	2.397	0.017	Significant	0.722	1.386

Source: *Researcher's Computation, 2021*

*Dependent Variable=FP

From Table 4.6 above, RC indicated positive and significant influence on FP (P-value<0.05); LC indicated positive and significant influence on FP (P-value<0.05);

TSA indicated positive and significant influence on FP (P-value<0.05) and FR showed positive and significant influence on FP (P-value<0.05). The Tolerance and the VIF for each of the independent variables in the study was not less than 0.1 and greater than 10, respectively. This showed that there was no multi-collinearity in each of the independent variables as stated earlier from the correlation matrix computed above on Table 4.4. A percentage increase in RC brought about 85.9% increase in FP; a percentage increase in LC brought about 17.0% increase in FP; a percentage increase in TSA brought about 14.1% increase in FP and a percentage increase in FR brought about 9.6% increase in FP. The constant value in the model showed that FP was 133.3% as all the independent variables (RC, LC, TSA and FR) were zero and significant (P-value<0.05). All the independent variables of RC, LC, TSA and FR were in compliance with the apriori expectation of the model.

Hypothesis One

H₀: Reporting compliance does not significantly influence fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector.

H₁: Reporting compliance significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector.

From Table 4.6 above, since the p-value is less than 0.05 (p-value<0.05) for RC, therefore, the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that reporting compliance significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Legislative control does not significantly influence fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector.

H₁: Legislative control significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria's public sector.

From Table 4.6 above, since the p-value<0.05 for LC, therefore, the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that legislative control significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: Treasury Single Account (TSA) does not significantly influence fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

H₁: Treasury Single Account (TSA) significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

From Table 4.6 above, since the $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ for TSA, therefore, the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that Treasury Single Account (TSA) significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

Hypothesis Four

H₀: Financial regulation does not significantly influence fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

H₁: Financial regulation significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

From Table 4.6 above, since the $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ for FR, therefore, the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that financial regulation significantly influences fiscal prudence in Nigeria public sector.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the result of the findings, the researchers concluded that plethora of financial regulatory laws put in place to regulate the activities of government institutions saddled with the responsibility of managing public wealth for the common good of the citizens influence accountability in the Nigerian public sector. However, for effective accountability, the following recommendations were made from the findings:

- (I) Government should strengthen regulatory institutions to enable them discharge their responsibilities effectively
- (ii) Laws empowering these institutions that demand accountability should be reviewed regularly in line with the current realities and modern day society to ensure accountability
- (iii) The legislature should amend the extant laws regulating financial management and reporting to remove loopholes which some public office holder can explore to enrich themselves at the expense of the majority
- (iv) Stiffer penalty should be meted on every contravening behavior to serve as deterrent to others

- (v) The judicial system should be strengthened to decide cases of corruption and other illicit act that runs against the tenet of public accountability.

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